

Impacts of COVID-19 on Vegetable Farmers in Ojo, Lagos State: Implication for Integrating Youth Adaptive Strategies for Future Shock

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ABSTRACT

Vegetable production is an essential component of the food system, providing vital minerals and vitamins necessary for sustaining healthy living. This study investigated vegetable farmers' responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in Ojo Local Government Area, Lagos State, with emphasis on integrating youth adaptive strategies for future shock. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 96 respondents. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and interview schedules, and analyzed with descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and means, while Chi-square and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were employed to test the hypotheses. Findings revealed that the most severe effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on vegetable production were loss of capital ($\bar{x} = 1.59$), loss of customers ($\bar{x} = 1.44$), and disruption of marketing activities ($\bar{x} = 1.38$). The major coping strategies adopted by farmers included home delivery within their neighborhoods (88.5%) and price reductions to attract buyers (79.2%). Farmers relied on family labour (79.2%), livelihood diversification (74.0%), and reduction of household expenses (72.9%). Furthermore, sex ($\chi^2 = 9.674$; $p = 0.002$) and years of education ($r = -0.315$; $p = 0.002$) significantly influenced the coping strategies adopted. The study revealed that COVID-19 significantly disrupted vegetable production and marketing, increasing farmers' vulnerability and food insecurity. Therefore, specialized training in resilient farming practices, digital marketing and cooperative management is important to prepare youth for future shocks. Promoting youth engagement in farmer-based organizations can enhance access to inputs, credit and collective marketing are recommended for building adaptive capacity and support for farming.

Keywords: Vegetable production, Covid-19 pandemic, Coping strategies, Food security.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains one of the most vulnerable sectors to global uncertainties and natural shocks, owing to its dependence on environmental, social, and economic stability (FAO, 2019). The emergence of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) first identified in Wuhan, China in December 2019 and subsequently declared a global pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) posed unprecedented challenges to agricultural systems worldwide (Adhikari et al., 2020). The pandemic generated severe macroeconomic disruptions, destabilizing production, distribution and trade, while exacerbating unemployment and deepening poverty levels across nations (World Bank, 2020). Among the hardest hit were farm workers and unskilled laborers, many of whom lost their livelihoods during prolonged lockdowns (International Labour Organization, ILO, 2020).

In developing economies such as Nigeria, where agriculture is the mainstay of rural livelihoods and a critical driver of food security and national income (Ojo & Adebayo, 2019), the pandemic magnified

existing production constraints especially among smallholder farmers, who dominate Nigeria's agricultural landscape (Ayetoro, 2020). The crisis was especially severe for vegetable farmers because of the perishability of produce making the farmers highly vulnerable to COVID-19 restrictions, as market closures, transportation bottlenecks and labor shortages drastically reduced sales, incomes and household food security (FAO, 2020; Ayanlade & Radeny, 2020).

Yet, the crisis also catalyzed innovation and adaptation. Farmers and stakeholders adopted coping strategies such as shifting toward subsistence farming, home-based food processing and diversification of market outlets, even if it required accepting lower farmgate prices (Ojo et al., 2021). Digital platforms and e-commerce solutions gained traction, enabling farmers to connect directly with consumers (Mhlanga, 2020). Technological interventions also emerged; for instance, Nigerian cleantech firm Ecotutu deployed solar-powered cold storage systems that helped reduce post-harvest losses and extend the shelf life of fresh

produce (Ecotutu, 2020). These adaptive responses highlighted the growing relevance of resilience, sustainability and technology in sustaining agricultural productivity during crises. Beyond immediate coping mechanisms, COVID-19 revealed important lessons for strengthening food systems over the long term. It emphasized the urgency of investing in mechanization, rural infrastructure and storage technologies to minimize post-harvest losses (FAO, 2020), while also reaffirming the role of localized food production and shorter supply chains in enhancing food security (OECD, 2020). Furthermore, the pandemic reshaped consumer preferences, fueling increased demand for fresh, locally produced and nutrient-dense foods that support immunity and overall health (Dudeja & Bhatia, 2020).

Understanding the multifaceted effects of COVID-19 on vegetable production is therefore critical for informing policy, research and practice. By examining the dual narrative of vulnerabilities and adaptive responses among smallholder farmers, this study contributes to ongoing discourse on building resilient, inclusive and sustainable food systems and pathways toward preparedness for future shocks.

Objective of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to assess post-covid resilience among vegetable farmers in Ojo, Lagos State: pathways for youth preparedness for future shock.

Specifically, the study sought to:

1. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents;
2. assess the effects of COVID-19 on vegetable farmers;
3. examine the response strategies adopted by vegetable farmers to mitigate the effects of the pandemic; and
4. identify the recovery strategies employed by farmers in the post-pandemic period.

Hypothesis of the study

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of respondents and coping strategies against the COVID-19 pandemic.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Ojo Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State, Nigeria. Ojo Local Government Area in Lagos State is a key peri-urban hub for vegetable production. The study area occupies approximately 180 square kilometers, of which about 30% is riverine. Geographically located in the southeastern part of the Lagos metropolis, the area is

highly cosmopolitan, hosting diverse populations from different regions of Nigeria. It is notable for its concentration of urban vegetable farmers; whose primary markets are urban consumers within Lagos city. The agro-ecological setting is within the southern rainforest zone of the humid tropics, characterized by low-lying terrain and favorable conditions for vegetable production. Commonly cultivated vegetables include okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*), celosia (*Celosia argentea*), lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*), *Corchorus olitorius*, and *Amaranthus* spp.

The study was conducted in Ojo Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State, Nigeria. Ojo LGA is characterized by intensive vegetable cultivation due to its favorable agro-ecological conditions, proximity to major markets and access to urban consumers. The area comprises both peri-urban and rural communities where vegetable farming constitutes a major source of livelihood for many households. The target population for the study comprised all *registered vegetable farmers* within Ojo Local Government Area, as obtained from the official records of the Lagos State Agricultural Development Authority and the local farmers' associations. The farmers were engaged in the production of common vegetables such as *Amaranthus* spp., *Telfairia occidentalis* (fluted pumpkin), *Celosia argentea* (soko), and *Lycopersicon esculentum* (tomato). A simple random sampling technique was adopted to ensure equal representation and minimize selection bias. A total of 96 respondents were randomly selected for the study from the list of 105 vegetable farmers. The sample size was considered adequate to provide reliable and representative data for statistical analysis and inference. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire complemented by interview schedule to capture responses from less literate farmers. The instrument was carefully designed to align with the study objectives. Data obtained were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16. Frequency counts, percentages and mean scores were used to summarize socio-economic characteristics, perceived effects and adaptation strategies. Chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the stated hypothesis. The effects of COVID-19 on vegetable farmers were measured using a three-point scale of very serious = 2, serious = 1, and no effect = 0. Mean values were calculated for each of the effects. Post-COVID-19 strategies were assessed using a list of options, with responses scored as 1 for "yes" and 0 for "no." Overall effects was computed using the mean index. Scores greater than or equal the mean value was regarded as high effects while scores less than the mean were tagged low effect.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

The results in Table 1 indicate that 49.0% of respondents were male, showing that women slightly dominate vegetable production in the study area. This agrees with Fapojuwo et al. (2022), who reported higher female involvement in vegetable farming due to its household and subsistence orientation. Despite their strong participation, women still face challenges such as limited access to land, credit, and extension services, which can limit their productivity (Adesugba & Mavrotas, 2016). The age distribution shows that 43.8% of respondents were between 41–50 years, while only 2.1% were above 60 years, with a mean age of 47 years. This indicates that most respondents are in their economically active years. The age structure became particularly relevant, as middle-aged and younger farmers were more likely to access, understand, and apply information on health protocols, market adjustments, and digital advisory services than older farmers, who often faced greater vulnerability and limited access to information channels. Findings show that most respondents were married (83.3%), while 11.5% were single. The dominance of married farmers suggests that vegetable production plays a key role in supporting household needs. This aligns with Ajetomobi et al. (2020), who noted that married farmers are more committed to farming due to household food demands. Findings on educational qualifications show that 56.3% of respondents had secondary education, 28.1% had primary education, and 15.6% had tertiary education, with an average of 10 years of schooling. This indicates a generally literate farming population. Education is known to improve farmers' ability to understand and adopt new practices. Ayanlade et al. (2017) associate literacy with climate-smart adoption, while Olanrewaju et al. (2019)

Effects of COVID-19 on vegetable production

Results presented in Table 2 show that the most severe effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on vegetable production were loss of capital ($\bar{x} = 1.59$), loss of customers ($\bar{x} = 1.44$) and disruption of marketing activities ($\bar{x} = 1.38$). The findings highlight how the pandemic directly undermined farmers' income streams and limited their access to buyers and markets. This aligns with Lucas (2020), report that prolonged lockdowns led to sharp declines in

link higher education to uptake of modern techniques. This literacy level is crucial for farmers in accessing timely information on health guidelines, market disruptions. Results show that 47.9% of respondents had 5–8 household members, 35.4% had 1–4 while 16.7% had 9 or more, with an average household size of six. This relatively large household structure is typical of Nigeria and provides both family labour and increased consumption needs. Larger households became especially important, as restrictions and labour shortages during COVID-19 meant farmers relied more on family members for farm work and meeting household food needs. Majority of the respondents (90.6%) cultivated between 1–4 acres, while only 9.4% farmed 5 acres or more, with an average farm size of 2 acres. This confirms the smallholder nature of vegetable production in the area. Such small farm sizes limit economies of scale and heighten vulnerability to shocks. Findings show that 34.4% of respondents had less than 10 years of experience, 65.6% had between 11–20 years while 1.0% had more than 20 years. The mean year of experience was 12 years. This indicates that most farmers possessed considerable practical knowledge. Farming experience is known to strengthen farmers' ability to manage risks and adapt to changing conditions such as market disruptions, input shortages, and movement restrictions during COVID-19. Only 9.4% of respondents had access to credit, with most relying on personal or informal sources such as savings (50%), cooperatives (17.7%), friends and family (7.3%), and moneylenders or banks (6.3%). Limited credit access constrains smallholder productivity, reducing their ability to scale production or adopt improved practices. Labour for vegetable production was mainly provided by family members (66.7%), followed by hired workers (18.8%) and personal effort (14.6%). The results reflect financial constraints that limit the hiring of labour. Reliance on family labour increased due to restrictions on worker mobility (Njap, 2021).

vegetable production and sales and with Swinnen (2020), that movement restrictions disrupted vegetable value chains globally, particularly for highly perishable crops. Other significant effects include restricted interaction with cooperative members ($\bar{x} = 1.36$) and reduced farmland cultivated ($\bar{x} = 1.23$), suggesting that many farmers scaled down operations while losing the support and resource-sharing benefits of farmer-to-farmer networks.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents (n= 96)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Sex			
Male	47	49.0	
Female	49	51.0	
Age (years)			
31 – 40	23	24.0	
41 – 50	42	43.8	
51 – 60	29	30.2	47years ± 1.05
More than 60 years	2	2.1	
Marital status			
Single	11	11.5	
Married	80	83.3	
Divorced	4	4.2	
Widowed	1	1.0	
Years spent on educational			
1 - 6 (Primary education)	27	28.1	
7 - 12 (Secondary education)	54	56.3	
More than 12 years (Tertiary education)	15	15.6	10years ± 0.83
Household size			
1 - 4			
5 - 8	34	35.4	
≥ 9	46	47.9	
Size of farmland (acre)			
1 – 4	16	16.7	6 members ± 0.17
≥ 5	87	90.6	
Year of farming experience			
Less than 10	9	9.4	2acres ± 1.34
11 – 20	47	49.0	
≥ 20	48	50.0	
Access to credit facilities			
Yes	1	1.0	12years ± 0.78
No	33	34.4	
Source of capital for farming			
Personal saving	63	65.6	
Friend/family	48	50.0	
Commercial banks	7	7.3	
Bank of Agriculture	13	13.5	
Cooperative	5	5.2	
Money lenders	17	17.7	
Source of labour			
Family	6	6.3	
Hired	64	66.7	
Personal	18	18.8	
	14	14.6	

Source: Field survey, 2023

Obayelu et al. (2021) similarly observed that Nigerian smallholders reduced production during the pandemic due to heightened uncertainty and limited access to inputs. Increased labour charges ($\bar{x} = 0.03$) on the other hand were of minimal concern because many workers accepted lower wages owing to reduced alternative job opportunities during the lockdown. This observation agrees with Madzorera et al. (2021) reported that shifts

in agricultural labour dynamics were as a result of reduced employment opportunities in other sectors. Overall, 62.5% of respondents reported experiencing severe effects, stressing vulnerability of vegetable farmers to external shocks. This finding corroborates Oluwafemi et al. (2020), submission that severity of pandemic impacts was closely tied to the perishability of produce and the fragility of informal market

systems. These results suggest that strengthening farmer cooperatives, expanding digital marketing platforms, and enhancing access to affordable credit

will be critical to mitigating similar shocks in the future.

Table 2: Effects of covid- 19 on vegetable production

Effects of covid- 19 on vegetable production	Mean (x)
Loss of capital	1.59*
Reduction in yield	0.97
Restriction of access to extension services	0.73
Restriction of interaction with fellow farmers	1.36*
Scarcity of labour	1.07*
Increased charges of labour	0.03
Scarcity of farm input	0.86
Increased cost of farm input	0.88
Disruption of production calendar	0.99
Reduction in size of farmland cultivated	1.23*
Disruption of marketing activities	1.38*
Loss of customers	1.44*
Grand mean	12.53
Mean level	1.04

*= Values above the mean level

Overall effect: Low effect 36 (37.5%)

High effect 60 (62.5%)

Source: Field survey, 2023

Vegetable farmers coping strategies during COVID-19

The results in Table 3 indicate that the most prominent coping strategies employed by vegetable farmers during the COVID-19 pandemic were home delivery within their neighborhoods (88.5%) and price reductions to attract buyers (79.2%). This underscore farmers’ reliance on short, informal marketing channels as a means of sustaining sales during movement restrictions. Reliance on family labour (59.4%) also emerged as a significant strategy, reflecting the reduced availability of hired labour and the necessity to minimize production costs. The

findings are consistent with Adepoju et al. (2020), noted that farmers in Osun State coped with the pandemic largely by cutting costs and relying on family-based resources. Similarly, Ojo et al. (2021) observed that direct-to-consumer marketing became the most reliable outlet for highly perishable crops during lockdowns. Conversely, online advertisement (22.9%) and enterprise diversification (22.9%) were the least adopted coping strategies. This suggests that digital marketing remained underdeveloped among vegetable farmers and that diversification required financial and technical resources that were difficult to mobilize during the crisis period.

Table 3: Vegetable farmers coping strategies during covid-19 (n= 96)

Coping strategies during covid-19	Freq. (%)
Diversification	22(22.9)
Home delivery within the neighborhood	85(88.5)
Reduction of price	76(79.2)
Used family labour	57(59.4)
Online advertisement	22(22.9)

Source: Field survey, 2023

Recovery strategies against COVID-19 pandemic

Table 4 reveals that the most common recovery strategies adopted by farmers were use of family labour (79.2%), livelihood diversification (74.0%) and

reduction of household expenses (72.9%). This shows how farmers leaned on household resources and alternative income sources to rebuild stability after the pandemic shock. Other notable strategies include

hawking vegetables within the neighborhood (60.4%) and seeking social support/palliatives (52.1%), indicating that informal marketing and community support systems were vital during recovery. The findings align with Yusuf et al. (2022), that diversification and cost-cutting were key recovery responses among farmers in Taraba State. Conversely, selling household assets (7.3%) was the least adopted

strategy, suggesting that most farmers avoided depleting long-term resources despite financial pressures. The implication is that recovery among vegetable farmers relied heavily on self-help and community-based strategies, while formal institutional support remained limited, underscoring the need for policies that expand access to affordable credit, extension services, and structured safety nets.

Table 4: Recovery strategies against covid-19 pandemic (n=96)

Recovery strategies	Freq. (%)
Reduce food consumption	57(59.4)
Livelihood diversification	71(74.0)
Reduce household expenses	70(72.9)
Source cheaper food stuff	34(35.4)
Apply for low interest loan	43(44.8)
Hawking of vegetable within the neighborhood	58(60.4)
Adoption of improved method of production	47(49.0)
Social support/palliative	50(52.1)
Seek family support	18(18.8)
Sold household assets	7(7.3)
Use of family labour	76(79.2)

Source: Field survey, 2023

Test of relationship between socio-economic characteristics of respondents and coping strategies of COVID-19

Table 5 shows that sex ($\chi^2 = 9.674$; $p = 0.002$) and years of education ($r = -0.315$; $p = 0.002$) significantly influenced coping strategies adopted by vegetable farmers during COVID-19. This implies that female farmers were more likely to adopt coping measures, a finding consistent with Fapojuwo et al. (2022), who reported that women are often more adaptive in vegetable production due to their central role in marketing and household food provision. Similarly, the

influence of education aligns with Olanrewaju et al. (2019), who noted that more educated farmers are better able to analyze challenges and make informed decisions in adopting new strategies. On the other hand, variables such as marital status, household size, and farming experience were not significant, suggesting that family structure and years of farming alone did not determine coping responses. These results emphasize the importance of targeting education and gender-sensitive interventions when designing resilience and adaptation programmes for farmers.

Table 5: Test of relationship between socio-economic characteristics of respondents and coping strategies of covid- 19

Socio-economic variables	Chi-square	r	df	p-value	Decision
Sex	9.674		1	0.002	Significant
Marital status	8.723		3	0.819	Not significant
Years of education		-0.315	95	0.002	Significant
Household size		-0.110	95	0.286	Not significant
Years of farming experience		-0.061	95	0.557	Not significant

Source: Field survey, 2023

Implications for integrating youths' adaptive strategies for future shock

COVID-19 pandemic exposed significant vulnerabilities among smallholder vegetable farmers, particularly their dependence on informal markets, physical labor, and unstable supply chains. Lockdowns, market closures, transport restrictions,

and labor shortages disrupted food distribution systems and highlighted the fragility of traditional farming structures (FAO, 2020; Reardon et al., 2020). Yet, farmers' adaptive responses such as increased reliance on family labor, localized marketing, and direct home deliveries, demonstrated practical resilience strategies with strong potential for future crisis management (Adhikari et al., 2020; Morton, 2020).

Positioning youth at the center of these adaptive processes offers an opportunity to strengthen agricultural resilience more sustainably. Youth possess distinct characteristics digital literacy, openness to innovation, risk-taking ability, and strong entrepreneurial motivation that make them well-suited to drive transformation in vegetable production systems. The attributes can enhance the effectiveness of resilience strategies that emerged during COVID-19. For instance, youths' proficiency with smartphones, social media, and online platforms can expand digital marketing, e-commerce, and mobile logistics systems, reducing overdependence on vulnerable physical markets (Aday & Aday, 2020; Stephens et al., 2020). The creativity of youth can also support the design of neighborhood delivery networks, online order aggregation, and market information systems that can function even under mobility restrictions.

Furthermore, engagement of youth can accelerate the uptake of climate-smart and labor-saving technologies such as small-scale mechanization, solar-powered irrigation, improved storage facilities, and digital advisory tools, which collectively help minimize post-harvest losses and ensure a more stable food supply during disruptions (Béné, 2020). Prioritizing young farmers' access to credit, essential inputs, training, and agribusiness incubation will significantly strengthen their ability to innovate and develop resilient agricultural enterprises (World Bank, 2021). Their involvement also introduces new ideas and approaches across the value chain from processing and packaging to branding and distribution ultimately making vegetable production more competitive, efficient, and

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appealing. Therefore, insights from the COVID-19 experience highlight the importance of a systems-oriented, youth-inclusive approach to agricultural resilience that combines traditional farming with technological innovation and entrepreneurial strategies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concluded that smallholder farmers, though relatively educated and reliant on family labour, were significantly affected by COVID-19 through loss of capital and customers, reduced farm size, and disrupted marketing channels. These impacts underscored their vulnerability, largely driven by dependence on informal markets and limited access to credit. Farmers responded to the challenges of the pandemic by delivering produce within their neighborhoods, reducing prices, and increasing their reliance on family labour. Post-pandemic recovery strategies included livelihood diversification, reduced household expenses, community support, and continued reliance on family labour. However, farmers' overall resilience remained constrained by weak market structures and inadequate institutional support. It is therefore recommended that engagement of youth farmers in capacity building, digital marketing skills, climate-smart innovations, and agribusiness training is crucial for strengthening long-term resilience. Additionally, improving digital literacy and encouraging the use of mobile applications, social media, and e-commerce platforms will reduce dependence on informal markets and create more stable, diversified marketing channels, thereby improving the sector's adaptability to future shocks.

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